

Dental Management of Children With Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation, Autism & Epilepsy : A Review

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Abstract

Children are our future society and assuring their healthy growth and development must be the most important consideration for all. Children with special health care needs (SHCN) have compromised oral health condition as it may be directly or indirectly associated to their disabilities. There is an increased prevalence of gingival diseases and dental caries among Children with SHCN due to poor oral hygiene. Sadly, the significance of dental care for these children has often been missed by the health care workers. The more compromised their general health conditions, the more dental care needs they have. During earlier days, providing basic dental care was the prime concern, but in recent years, the dental profession has emphasized more on complete oral health care to the special health care needs children. Pediatric Dentistry is a specialized branch that provides primary, comprehensive, preventive and therapeutic oral health care to children with Special Health Care Needs.

Children with Special Health Care Needs may experience challenges in many ways such as intellectual disability, physical disability, medical disability, Genetic disability and learning disability. The document addresses intellectually challenged patients including Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation, Epilepsy and Autism.

Co-ordination and Consultation with medical and other dental professionals may be required for cautious delivery of oral health care and to enhance long term good results for such patients.

Keywords:

Special Health Care Needs Children, Intellectually challenged, Dental Management of Special Children, Behaviour Management, Oral hygiene.

Introduction

The birth of a child is an occasion of great happiness and joy and is always eagerly awaited by the family members, but when it becomes evident that something is inappropriate with their neonate, their entire world is made into pieces from a whole. The parents of such children start suffering from anger and denial. The child may be nurtured with great love and affection as he grows but, at times, the parents may express their anger on the child who suffers without his own fault. It is difficult to maintain general and oral health of such children and their dentition may be damaged by caries and periodontal diseases. Hence the management of these "God's forgotten children" is a task which needs special effort on the part of the dental surgeon and pediatric dentist^[1].

Children with special health care needs are those who have certain disability that restricts them in performing daily life activities. They experience higher health care utilization and

expenditures than the average paediatric population. Individuals with special health care needs may be at an increased risk for oral diseases, that can have a direct and devastating impact on the general health of special children^[2]. In India about 6-10% of children are born disabled and one-third of the total disabled population is comprised of children^[3]. Conditions like Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder(ADHD), Autism, Down's Syndrome, Congenital Heart Disease, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Systemic Diseases become a great challenge for the Special health care needs children affecting their overall quality of life so their requirements are also distinctive, and need specialized, multidisciplinary approach for their oral health care^[4-6].

The American Academy of Paediatric Dentistry (AAPD) accepted that delivering primary, comprehensive, preventive and therapeutic oral health care to children with special health care needs is a crucial part in the

speciality of paediatric dentistry. We should consider the unique qualities of each person and the need to ensure maximum health for all, regardless of developmental disability or other special health care needs.

Special Health Care Needs (AAPD, 2013)^[7]

Defined as “any physical, developmental, mental, sensory, behavioural, cognitive, or emotional impairment or limiting condition that requires medical management, health care intervention, and/or use of specialized services or programs”. This condition sometimes imposes limitations in performing daily self-maintenance activities, can be because of or substantial limitations in a major life activity.

Common Oral Health Problems in Special Needs Care Children

Special health care needs children commonly experiences the following oral health problems : Delayed, accelerated or inconsistent tooth eruption, Dental caries, Periodontal disease, Malocclusion, Abnormal oral habits, Tooth anomalies, Trauma and injury, Enamel hypoplasia, Dental erosion and behaviour problems. There are also some **contributing factors to oral health problems in children with special needs care such as** Genetic disorders, Reduced salivary flow, Antiepileptic Drugs, Physical limitations, Diet restriction and Difficulty in brushing and flossing^[4].

Design of Dental Office

One of the first prerequisite in managing a disabled child is accessibility of dental offices. It needs foundation of barrier-free facilities for people with all kinds of disabilities.

Figure 1 :-Dental clinic design for children with special health care needs -
 1. Dental chair, 2. Papoose board, 3. Nitrous oxide inhalation sedation apparatus,
 4. Wheelchair, 5. Doctor's chair, 6. Assistant's stool^[1].

The width of doorways should be more i.e. should be 32 inch wider than normal. Providing wheelchair turning space, design of operatory should allow movement of dental chair, instrument control unit and suction system. To match the wheelchair design dental chairs should be adjustable. Parking lot, Walk away, Entrance door steps/ ground level, Railing 1:12, Floor of the entrance (non slipping), Entrance calling bell, Space for wheelchair and transportation, Telephone, Rest room, Space in the operatory, Mobile units, and mobile dental services should be there.

Protective Stabilization

There is difficulty in controlling extremities of infants or patients with certain neuromuscular disorders so partial or complete protective stabilization of such patients becomes necessary and also effectively supports in diagnosing and delivering dental care^[8].

Part immobilized	Name
Body	Triangular sheet, Papoose board, Pedi-wrap, Beanbag dental chair insert Safety belt & Extra assistant
Extremities	Posey straps, Velcro straps, Towel and tape and Extra assistant
Head	Forearm body support, Head positioner, Plastic bowl and Extra assistant
Intraoral	Molt's mouth prop, Mckesson bite blocks, Wrapped tongue blades & Open wide disposable mouth prop

Table 1 : Classification of specialized equipments^[9].

Children with Special Health Care Needs may experience challenges in many ways. Disabilities include intellectual disability, physical disability, medical disability, Genetic disability and learning disability.

Dental Management of Intellectually Challenged Children

Intellectual challenges include Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation, Epilepsy and Autism.

Cerebral Palsy

Is one of the most severely handicapping condition affecting approximately 2-2.5 per 1000 live births. It is a disorder of posture and movement caused due to non-progressive abnormality of the immature brain that originates during the prenatal or perinatal period and results in significant impairment of functional mobility^[7]. Oral manifestations include loss of tooth structure due to GERD, Gingival hyperplasia because of long term medication, frequent tongue thrust during speaking, malaligned anteriors, jaw dislocation is common due to abrupt opening of the mouth.

During dental examination or treatment of children with CP schedule appointments early mornings. Obtain medical records prior to the first appointment, and arrange necessary consultation. An extensive oral examination should be completed on all patients. If the patient is unable to provide accurate information, may require help of family members. The dental treatment plan should be formulated according to accepted dental practice and take into consideration the following factors: Mental age of the patient, Understanding and communication level, Psychological needs, Physical limitations, Accessibility issues, Medical conditions, Antibiotic prophylaxis^[1].

Use behaviour management technique to obtain desired behaviour such as voice control tell-show-do(TSD), modelling. In case of severely affected child verbal command should be repeated. As these patients have severe gag reflex there may be difficulty in taking dental radiographs. Extra oral techniques such as **oblique head plate** and **reverse bitewing technique can be used in such patients**. When molars are involved, prefer placing stainless steel crowns over restorations. Myofunctional therapy should be incorporated during the growing years of the child because it strengthens the facial muscles and turns the inactive lip into active one. It also prevents flaring and malocclusion as it keep the tongue at its place. The dentist should Counsel the parents regarding oral hygiene maintenance, growth and development of orofacial disparity occurring due to such condition. Emphasize the importance of diet and Preventive treatment modalities like topical fluoride application and significance of recall appointments^[10].

Adjust the Dental chair carefully and slightly tip the chair back to provide a position of security. There is severe head- and-neck involvement in spastic type of a patient so they require more control and support, are suggested to sit on the parent's or assistant's knee, leaning back against the right shoulder. If the patient is on a wheelchair, the treat him/her in the wheelchair itself. Head stability can be achieved by the help of Velcro straps, and open mouth can be maintained with the use of mouth props. To restrain the arms and legs Canvas straps equipped with Velcro fasteners can be used. A dentist should avoid unexpected movements which may trigger muscle spasm. He should be gentle and caring.

Malocclusion is quite severe in CP patients. There is a risk of caries and enamel hypoplasia so Orthodontic treatment may not be a treatment option. The success of orthodontic treatment actually depends on the potential of the patient or the caretaker to maintain good daily oral hygiene. Now a days, certain technological advancements are done in dentistry which could help disabled dental patients for their orthodontic treatment. They include taking impressions using quickset materials, use of self-etching bonding agent, self-ligating brackets, and use of reversible mini-implant anchorage. Orthodontic treatment become less difficult in CP children after careful patient selection. Success of the treatment depends on type and severity of malocclusion and the amount of patient cooperation.

In CP patients, there is an increase risk of dental trauma as there is uncontrolled head movement. Thus, lip seal acts as a barrier. The prevention of future trauma and the treatment of traumatized teeth should be of primary concern. A pedodontist should educate the parents, caregivers and teachers regarding correct emergency care of CP patients after trauma, to look for preventive measures, like cautious transfer of patients in wheelchairs, use of mouth guards, padding of objects and hard surfaces, and Also highlight the emergency measures to caregivers in dental trauma and explain the steps to follow if a permanent tooth is knocked out. Suggest a tooth-saving. Also, instruct caregivers to find any missing pieces of a fractured tooth. Also explain them that in case of foreign body aspiration patient's chest x-ray is essential. Children with developmental disabilities are found to be more physically abused as compared to general population. In case of any suspect of child abuse come across, contact Child Protective Services agency immediately.

One of the most common finding in CP patient is Bruxism. If it is severe and constant may cause premature wearing of the teeth. The treatment options for Bruxism includes restorations, occlusal adjustments, use of oral splints, extraction, and pharmacological management. In patients with severe visual impairment Sleep disorders may also predispose to the development of nocturnal bruxism. Before suggesting mouth guards or bite splints in CP patients Gagging problems must be observed as it may make them uncomfortable and will not wear them. Features such as hypotonia and open bite causes drooling which affects daily oral care.

Periodontal disease is also common in children with CP. Major factor contributing periodontal disease is because of antiepileptic drugs, most commonly phenytoin. Gingival hyperplasia is predictive for periodontal diseases. The pedodontist should teach caregivers about oral hygiene and demonstrate proper brushing techniques to them. An antimicrobial agent such as chlorhexidine is recommended for daily use. Patient with swallowing problems, faces difficulty in mouth rinse so chlorhexidine can be applied using a spray bottle or toothbrush and is equally effective as rinsing.

Because of inadequate oral hygiene Dental caries is frequent among CP patient. Factors contributing to the development of dental caries are biological, economic, cultural, environmental, and social factors. The dentist should guide the caretaker to make a patient drink water regularly, give sugar-free medicines if possible, and rinse mouth after taking any medicine also to provide substitute to cariogenic foods and beverages. Preventive measures such as fluorides and pit and fissure sealants should be recommended.

Dental erosion is commonly seen in CP patient generally who are predisposed to GERD. By diagnosing early signs of dental erosion in CP patients, the Dentists can provide proper preventive therapy and can refer the patient for treatment of GERD. Diagnosis of early signs help in preventing irreversible damage to dentition. The dentist should teach the parents or caregivers

correct tooth brushing techniques. Horizontal scrub method is the most common technique recommended as it is quite easy to perform and can give good results. Electric toothbrushes have also been recommended for disabled children. Parents or caregiver should always help the child to brush their teeth, and the child's head must always be supported. There is presence of sucrose in almost all of the medications which are prescribed to children. Thus, a child on oral medications must get their teeth cleansed after each medication^[11-13].

It may be difficult to manage CP patient at times, in such cases sedation and anesthesia is needed. Most commonly if invasive procedures are required^[14,15]. Patients with history of respiratory problems and convulsions represent a specific challenge so prior to the required procedure, evaluation by the related specialty (pediatrics, anesthesia, and/or neurology) is often needed. If the procedure involves prolonged period of decreased oral intake, oral medications can be replaced by intravenous antiepileptic drugs. Drugs which can be used are phenobarbitone or phenytoin, anyhow, a loading dose should be initiated before the procedure for optimal effects. Once the patient is able to take the oral drugs, discourage IV drugs quickly. Drugs like benzodiazepines, nitrous oxide, narcotics, and propofol can be used to induce sedation and anesthesia. Many children with severe mental disability are not able to tolerate initial facemask prior to IV sedation. But can be utilized in milder cases to avoid the fear and anxiety corresponding to IV insertion. The airway should be maintained throughout the procedure and Oxygen saturation should be monitored by pulse oximetry.

CP children are at higher risk of aspirating dental filling materials, debris from tooth preparation, or sometimes an extracted tooth. This is because of increased salivation and water spray used for cooling instruments. In these cases a throat shield should always be used to further protect the airway. Postoperative care involves keep the child restrained until he or she is able to respond to verbal commands or gets complete consciousness. IV cannulas and monitor should be removed as soon as possible as they add to the child's fear and anxiety.

Mental Retardation

Also called as intellectual development disorder (IDD) or general learning disability^[16]. Characterized by remarkable restrictions both in intellectual functioning like learning, reasoning, problem solving and in adaptive behaviour. **Oral manifestations** like Nursing bottle caries or ECC, Altered salivary flow due to multiple medications, malocclusions, fractured non vital teeth and soft tissue complications^[1]. Early loss of tooth structure, secondary caries, trauma and habits leads to speech impairment. Loss of space for the permanent dentition causing significant orthodontic problems, abnormal jaw development, change in mastication, affecting esthetics and a development of poor self-image and Halitosis.

Behavioural problems are one of the main barriers for individuals with special needs in accessing dental care and frequently represent a challenge for oral healthcare practitioner^[17]. **Desensitization** may be fruitful with some anxious patients. It should be the induction therapy. The first visit can be an introductory visit in which no actual treatment has to be done. While administering dental treatment to patients with disabilities the use of restraints is appreciated as acceptable dental practice when properly applied to control behaviour but it should be adopted only when there is failure of other techniques such as desensitization, TSD, etc. after taking an informed consent.

Those patients who cannot be managed with physical and chemical restraints are the optimal for the sedation procedure. Sedation and consulted behaviour management should be given with patient's physician, family and caregiver's consent. **Oral sedation** with Valium, Xanax, chloral hydrate, or hydroxyzine may be helpful in reducing patient anxiety during dental treatment. Good team and appropriate monitoring equipments **are** required for Intravenous sedation. The team must be well trained to respond to emergencies such as allergic, respiratory, and/or cardiac complications. General anesthesia should be the last resort in behaviour management. The treatment is advised for the non co-operative children or children who are too young to comprehend. The medical condition should be examined by the pediatrician and anesthetic before the child can be considered for the anesthesia.

Notice their brushing method first and demonstrate them the correct technique. A powered tooth brush can also be introduced in this situation. Reinforce the techniques to caregiver. Choose appropriate method as gargles in case of use of mouthwash. Patients with impaired swallowing reflex, spray works well. Along with restorative care, stress should be made on decreasing the occurrence of new caries in these patients by promoting non-cariogenic food and beverages as snacks and adding more water to their diet. Dentist should explain sugar free medicine and importance of rinsing with water after every meal and medications.

MR patients come across traumatic injuries very frequently; educate parent and caregiver with emergency management of knocked out or fractured tooth along with tooth preservation and instant professional care. Find out the mental, dental and skeletal age of the child and clinically correlate the dentition. For any congenitally nursing teeth, hypoplasia or developmental defects keep the child under observation. The occurrence of all these defects helps in determining if the patient has multiple problems or is syndromic MR.

An orthopantomogram (OPG) can be very beneficial because it is non invasive procedure and it's elaborate image covers complete dentition. Due to various drugs gingival overgrowth can occur, if the gingival tissues interfere with occlusion or oral hygiene Gingivectomy may be done. Electrosurgery or laser surgery techniques should also be viewed as an alternative in those patients who cannot tolerate periodontal packs well. Frequent recall visits are indicated (every 2-3 months) in these patients due to poor oral hygiene.

Glass ionomer cement releases fluoride so it is considered as more appropriate restoration for patients with a high caries. For restoring severely damaged teeth Stainless steel crowns are recommended. When the patient can cooperate tooth is restorable then Endodontic treatment should be considered. Single-appointment procedures are advisable. Use of an apex locator would be helpful as working-length radiographs would be tough to obtain. Fixed prosthodontics is preferred over removable if patient's oral compliance is present. For tooth preparation resin bonded bridges are more helpful and less time-consuming. Complete dentures are contraindicated in severe and profound MR and patients with poor muscle control.

Epilepsy

It is a group of disorders characterized by chronic, recurrent and paroxysmal changes in neurological function caused by abnormalities in the electrical activity of the brain. Each episode of neurologic dysfunction is called a seizure and the seizure may be convulsive when accompanied by motor manifestations or may be manifested by other changes in neurologic function. **Oral manifestations** include Gingival hyperplasia, Recurrent aphthous ulcers, Anomalous dental development like small teeth, delayed eruption, Cervical lymphadenopathy, Soft tissue lacerations of tongue or buccal mucosa, Trauma to teeth-avulsion, luxation and fractures^[18].

Management of seizures in the dental office can be best done by taking complete medical history regarding the type and frequency of seizure episodes before the treatment. Reduce the stress on the patients with psycho behavioural preparations, sedations etc. Since Diazepam has anticonvulsant properties, it is the drug of choice. Use of dental chair light is avoided. Avoid those drugs which promote seizure like phenothiazines, IV local anesthetics. Earlier dilantin sodium has been used for seizures, but nowadays new drugs like vigabatrin, lamotrigine, gabapentin and topiramate are used. Due to the use of antiepileptic medication (dilantin sodium), typical fibrous gingival hyperplasia may occur. Surgical removal may be necessary in certain cases and the child's physician can be consulted about a change in medication.

Appointments should be kept short. Stress the importance of tooth brushing procedures and regular dental review. The fixed type of appliances are preferred if indicated for tooth movement and tooth replacement. The patient should be placed in the lateral recumbent position and the chair is lowered to a supine position if the seizure occurs in the chair. The patient is protected from injuring himself by moving sharp objects away and do not place anything in the child's mouth during a seizure. The lips can be superficially suctioned to remove excessive secretions, but deep suctioning must be avoided, to prevent a gag-reflex and provocation of emesis.

Support a patent airway. Have supplemental oxygen available to use if needed. If the convulsions do not stop within a five minutes, medication should be administered. This can be rectal diazepam is 0.5 mg/kg upto a maximum of 10 mg. The dose for intranasal midazolam is 0.2 mg/kg up to a maximum of 10 mg. Emergency medical services/ambulance should be activated if

rescue medication has been used. Hospital admission via emergency department services should be arranged. Neurologists and paediatricians consent were taken during the entire treatment protocol.

Once the seizure gets over, Do not proceed further with dental treatment that day. The operator should try to talk to the patient to assess the level of consciousness during the post-ictal phase. Do not try to restrain the patient, as he or she might be disoriented. Evaluating the post-ictal phase, discharge the patient home with a responsible person, to his or her physician or to an emergency clinic for further valuation. When Seizure occurs during treatment, remove all dental instruments from the mouth. Clear the area around the dental chair. Turn child to one side and stay with him. Monitor airway to reduce risk of aspiration. Note time seizure begins. If seizure continues > 5 min call EMS-danger of Status Epilepticus (potentially life threatening)^[19].

Autism

It is a neuro-developmental disorder characterized by impaired communication and social interaction skills and repetitive and restricted behaviour and interests. It is called autism spectrum disorder since the manifestations of the disorder vary greatly amongst individual patients. **Oral manifestations include** Dental caries due to soft and sweetened foods and also pouching due to poor tongue co-ordination, difficulty in tooth brushing and flossing, Bruxism, tongue thrusting, picking at gingiva and lip biting which might account for the high rate of self-inflicted oral lesions.

The prevalence of traumatic teeth is higher among children with autism due to self-injury from head banging, picking or face tapping. Gingivitis and poor oral hygiene. The study 'Dental caries experience, oral health status and treatment needs of dental patients with autism' finds that autistic children exhibit poor oral hygiene, higher caries prevalence and unmet requirement for dental treatment as compared to non-autistic healthy children. Therefore those oral health program that stresses on prevention, should be appreciated and considered of great importance for autistic children and young people^[20].

Many of the drugs used to treat the associated features of autism have systemic side effects like CNS stimulants (methylphenidate, dextroamphetamine) - causes xerostomia and hypertensive episode also may occur if local anaesthetics with vasoconstrictors are given in excess or by inadvertent intravascular injections. Anticonvulsants (Carbamazepine and valproate) - When given along with aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, excessive bleeding may result. Erythromycin and clarithromycin may cause carbamazepine toxicity by inhibiting its metabolism in liver. Antipsychotic medications (Risperidone and olanzapine) - May induce motor disturbances affecting speech, swallowing and the use of removable prostheses, produce transient sialorrhea followed by xerostomia. Antidepressants (Fluoxetine and sertraline) - Xerostomia, dysgeusia (altered taste sensations), stomatitis and glossitis. Fluoxetine comes with a risk of developing involuntary orofacial movements, like sucking, smacking and protrusion of tongue.

For the dental treatment of an autistic patient several basic behaviour guidance methods have been suggested, which includes the presence of parents, tell-show-do technique, short, clear, and differential verbal commands. Visual pedagogy concept or combined use of shaping, reinforcement and sensory adaptation can also contribute in dental examination of the autistic child. Child with limited receptive skills and absence of joint attention, the use of reward statements may not provide the desired results during dental treatment. Younger autistic patient may behave better to certain management techniques like positive reinforcement. Therefore, there is a critical influence of child's age on social skills and in handling their behaviour.

Visual pedagogy that arouse aversive behaviour of the child may helpful in setting up favourable conditions for him or her to cooperate during dental treatment. The process known as functional behavioural assessment may take place during the pre-visit consultation of parents. To get the child familiarized with the dental operatory room, the dentist can arrange the home-centered preparation including acclimatization with dental instruments, educating skills essential for the dental examination by utilizing phrases such as 'open your mouth', and preparing custom-made photo books to help the child. The latter model takes advantage of the ability of children to make better contact by means of pictures instead of words^[21-23]. Video modelling is an effective method for developing various skills in children with autism such as social, communication and self-help skills.

Application of the TEACCH (Treatment and Education of Autistic and related Communication –handicapped children) concept to desensitize the children to dental procedures and oral hygiene procedures are usually effective in training the children in home and in clinic. The acceptance of toothbrush by the child can be increased by a kind introduction to tooth brushing using alternatives like washcloth, toothbrushes of various texture and design may upgrade. Children with severe bruxism and self-injurious habits prescribe mouth guard. Powered toothbrushes are recommended only when the child can tolerate^[24].

To calm the child papoose Board or Pedi-wrap and pre appointment conscious sedation may be important. Ask the child to sit alone in the dental chair and make him familiar with the dental setting. Approach the child in a quiet, nonthreatening manner. Eye contact is difficult to achieve and the children are prone to tantrums and aggressive or destructive behaviour. Using fingers, start the oral examination slowly and if successful, begin with dental instrument.

Do not make dental instruments visible to the child and also keep light out of the child's eyes. Reduce other sensory input such as loud noises, sudden movements and odours that may be distracting to the child. Reward co-operative behaviour with positive verbal reinforcement. Notice abnormal body movements and predict further movements. Keep area around the dental chair clear. Use the same staff at each visit if possible. Sedation must be used with accurate precautions and after physician consultation. Giving treatment in the operating room by using general anesthesia for complex surgical or restorative treatment is considered only if all other approaches fail.

Recent Advancements

Now a days many technological advancements have been achieved in the field of dental management of special children which have proven to refine skills and can be integrated by the pediatric dentists in their day-to-day clinical practice for successful dental treatment in this group of patients. Audio and video technologies have been shown good results in managing children with special healthcare needs. Computers inspire autistic children due to their predictability and steadiness as compared to uncertain human responses. The computer provides the child his/her independent functioning skills. Furthermore, smartphones and tablets are creating their way into clinical practice because of their many advantages.

Conclusion

The attitude and skills of dentists is the most important aspect for successful treatment of children with SHCN. Oral health is progressively considered as a foundation for general health, and a foremost indicator for the success of dental treatment. The parents, caregivers and teachers for children with special health care needs must become learned and competent in home oral health care. The role of the pediatric dentist is to enhance oral health and to motivate parents and caregivers for good home oral health practice. When a child with health care needs reach adulthood, his or her oral health care requirement may increase beyond the scope of the pediatric dentist's practice. The victorious transformation from pediatric to adult dental care is essential for the continuity of care and improvement in long- term prognosis of children with SHCN.

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